

Materials to Be Used in Future Magnetic Confinement used with Plasma: A Review

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Abstract

This paper presents the roadmap of the main materials to be used for ITER and DEMO class reactors as well as an overview of the most relevant innovations that have been made in recent years. The main idea in the EUROfusion development program for the FW (first wall) is the use of low-activation materials. Thus far, several candidates have been proposed: RAFM and ODS steels, SiC/SiC ceramic composites and vanadium alloys. In turn, the most relevant diagnostic systems and PFMs (plasma-facing materials) will be described, all accompanied by the corresponding justification for the selection of the materials as well as their main characteristics. Finally, an outlook will be provided on future material development activities to be carried out during the next phase of the conceptual design for DEMO, which is highly dependent on the success of the IFMIF-DONES facility, whose design, operation and objectives are also described in this paper.

Keywords: Nuclear Fusion, ITER, Plasma, design.

Introduction

The global energy outlook is currently going through a time of crisis and uncertainty as a result of the excessive use of and dependence on fossil fuels over the last century. This is why a transition to new energy sources must be urgently addressed, with the need to improve efficiency and opt for a decarbonized mix in which nuclear energy seems likely to play a key role. When talking about nuclear energy, one tends to think of the present day technology (fission), but the reality is that a new means of energy production that will completely change the current paradigm is getting closer every day. Nuclear fusion energy offers the prospect of a safe,

inexhaustible and waste-free energy source for generations to come. Despite this, it also presents certain science and engineering challenges that, so far, have been insurmountable due to the extreme conditions and plasma instabilities faced by the materials of these future reactors. The premise of this review is to try to analyze the horizon of new possibilities that the development of nuclear fusion is allowing and to contribute, as far as possible, to clarify what are and what could become the materials that will facilitate the success of ITER and in the future of DEMO.

Nuclear Fusion

Nuclear fusion is a reaction involving light atomic nuclei and nucleons, so that when two of these nuclei join to form a heavier one, energy is given off. It is the basis for the existence of stars like the Sun. This process initially requires the joining of a proton with another proton, an event known as the proton-proton chain, which was discovered in 1939 by the German physicist Hans Bethe [1].

Naturally, replicating this process on Earth requires in-depth research and development. Incidentally, there is one element of particular interest for fusion due to its simplicity and abundance, hydrogen, which is precisely the one used by the Sun. Specifically, two of its isotopes, deuterium (D) and tritium (T), are of interest.

This process is characterized as an exothermic reaction, where the nucleons must be very close (~ 1 fm) for the strong nuclear interaction to unite them and thus overcome the electromagnetic repulsion, called the Coulomb barrier. It is also necessary to reach temperatures of millions of degrees for this reaction to take place. Almost as soon as physicists learned that solar energy could only be the product of nuclear fusion, they discovered, however, that the temperature at the center of our star (about 15 million degrees) is insufficient for hydrogen nuclei to actually come together at the necessary distance. So how is it possible for nuclear fusion to occur in the Sun? To explain this, we must resort to quantum mechanics and one of its most renowned concepts, the tunnel effect, that allows certain particles to overcome the Coulombian energy barrier without actually reaching its maximum value. Despite this, it is still necessary to reach enormous temperatures indeed. This is why fusion is described as a thermonuclear process.

As mentioned above, the most viable reaction for the first generations of nuclear fusion reactors is the one between deuterium ($2H_2$) and tritium ($3H_3$) (**Figure 1**), obtaining 17.6 MeV of energy that translates into an alpha particle or He nucleus and a fast neutron.

Why use these H isotopes and not others? This is because the *cross section* (which defines the probability of success of a nuclear reaction between a target and an incident particle. Its SI unit is the barn, 1 barn = 10^{-28} m²) of this process is very high for relatively low temperatures.

Another fundamental reason is the availability of these isotopes. D can be easily found in seawater (an estimated 30 g/m³). T, on the other hand, is a radioactive and unstable element (decay constant $T_{1/2}=12.3$ years) which is produced naturally in small quantities when cosmic rays (98% protons) strike the H atoms present in the atmosphere. It can also be obtained as a product in CANDU NPP.

There are approximately 40 kilograms of T on the planet, so it is vital to find an alternative method to reproduce it on a large scale.

T breeding consists of irradiating a Li blanket with the neutrons produced in the fusion reaction itself (see Equation (2)). This generates the T that will supply the reactor. Definitely, this is one of the greatest technological challenges that ITER and its related projects will have to face.

On the other hand, natural lithium (92.5% ⁷Li y 7.5% ⁶Li) is an abundant element in the earth's crust (30 ppm) and is found in lower concentrations in the sea. The thickness of the blanket is large enough (~m) to slow down the neutrons produced by the fusion reactions. Upon impacting with the walls, their energy is transferred in the form of heat. This heats water that turns into steam, which is then used to turn a turbine and hence generate electricity. To get an idea of the efficiency of this process, the use of 1 kg of D-T has the energy equivalence of 8000 tons of oil.

The breeding blanket (BB) is one of the most complex and important components of future fusion reactors, as it is not only responsible for the extraction of energy but also for T breeding in order to have a self-sufficient facility (tritium breeding ratio, TBR >1) [2,3]. This parameter is

defined as the average number of T atoms bred per T atom burned. It should be higher than 1.15 in order to take into account T losses which cannot be avoided in a real fusion reactor [4].

Tritium transport modelling allows experts to predict how this element will move towards the systems that have to recover it in order to refuel the plasma. In doing so, two fundamental considerations must be taken into account. Firstly, tritium does not simply go from point A to B, as it is a gas that diffuses easily. This can happen especially at high temperatures, as it can enter and mix with materials in pipes, valves and other components along the way. Secondly, tritium is radioactive, so it is of great interest in terms of nuclear safety and radiological protection to know where it can accumulate.

There are two options for the commercial development of nuclear fusion, magnetic or inertial confinement. This review will look at the former, as it has become the more advanced option with a higher probability of success.

3. ITER: The Project That Might Change the Future

3.1. What Is ITER?

ITER is the most ambitious energy project in the world today and is located in the town of Cadarache in southern France (**Figure 2**). Up to 35 *nations* (the 27 countries of the EU together with Switzerland, the United Kingdom, China, India, Japan, Korea, Russia and the United States) are collaborating to build the world's largest *Tokamak* (Axisymmetric toroidal chamber characterized by a large toroidal magnetic field, moderate plasma pressure and relatively small toroidal current), a magnetic confinement fusion device designed to demonstrate the viability of fusion as a large-scale, carbon-free energy source.

Figure 2. Aerial view of the ITER site. Reprinted from Ref. Credit © ITER Organization, 2022.

In turn, the technologies, materials and physical regimes required for large-scale commercial electricity production will be tested.

Thousands of engineers and scientists have contributed to the design of ITER since the idea of a joint international fusion experiment was first launched in 1985. The participating members have committed themselves over a period of about 40 years to build and operate the experimental device until fusion reaches a point at which DEMO can be launched.

3.2. What Are the Main Objectives?

The amount of fusion energy a tokamak is capable of producing is a direct result of the number of fusion reactions taking place inside it. The larger the vessel, the greater the plasma volume and thus the greater the potential fusion energy. This has its trade-offs in terms of cost, which is usually the case in projects based on economies of scale, typical of traditional nuclear energy production. ITER has been specifically designed to:

1. Produce 500 MW of fusion energy.
2. Demonstrate the safety features of a fusion device.
3. Test the reproduction of T with TBM (Test Blanket Modules).
4. Demonstrate the integrated operation of technologies for a fusion plant.
5. Achieve a D-T plasma in which the reaction is maintained by internal heating

3.3. When Will the First Plasma Be Obtained?

The first ITER plasma is scheduled for December 2025. As of 31 July 2022, 77.1% of the work required for the first plasma has been completed

Beyond its symbolic importance, the first plasma will also be a litmus test for the project, as it will be the first occasion to verify the correct alignment of the machine's magnetic fields as well as the correct functioning of key systems (vacuum vessel, magnets, and critical plant systems).

The first plasmas will use H, He or a mixture of both. This is why the initial processes do not require a D-T fuel. Since many of the heating systems are optimized for D-T type plasmas in order to achieve *H-mode* (a high plasma confinement operating regime which is reached when a certain heating threshold is exceeded [8]), they will operate at a reduced intensity that will gradually increase over the years. The first low-power H-plasma, which will last a few milliseconds, will be followed by other "shots" of higher power and longer duration. Finally, the

first production of D-T fusion energy will take place during the nuclear phase of the machine, expected around 2035.

3.4. Materials Design Requirements

For the range of expected operating conditions (including possible accident scenarios) in ITER and with even greater relevance to DEMO, a qualified database must be generated to demonstrate that candidate materials meet a number of indispensable design requirements. Some of these are:

- Good strength, ductility and toughness.
- Radiation resistance and nonactivation properties after irradiation.
- Resistance to creep rupture, fatigue cracking and creep-fatigue interactions.
- Good resistance of mechanical and physical properties against The embrittlement.
- Acceptable chemical compatibility and corrosion resistance with fusion-specific breeder materials (e.g., Be, LiPb).

4. Plasma Facing Materials

One of the most sensitive processes taking place in a nuclear fusion reactor is the interaction with the hot plasma, which is at temperatures higher than the core of the sun. PFMs and PFCs are those materials/components that cover almost the entire internal surface of the VV and represent the interface between the plasma and the rest of the tokamak. They are part of two systems: the blanket (which includes the FW) and the divertor, which occupy areas of 610 and 140 m², respectively.

The lifetime of a PFM is limited from ~100 dpa (a dpa, displacements per atom, is the number of times that an atom is displaced a given fluence. It is a unit for quantifying irradiation damage that is strongly dependent on the material in question). The plasma-walls interaction processes are associated with thermal loads of up to 20 MW/m² in continuous thermal periods and can reach the GW/m² range when an ELM occurs. ITER will not only seek to demonstrate the feasibility of the D-T process but will also be the first test device for PFMs and PFCs in extreme radiation scenarios. Some of the most serious damaging mechanisms to be considered in these materials are:

T retention. (i)

(ii)

- H-bubble induced fragility. (iii)
- High velocity impacts of dust particles in the PFM. (iv)
- Possible degradation, transmutation and activation. (v)
- Thermally induced defects due to cracking and melting of PFM. (vi)
- Thermal fatigue damage produced in the joints between the PFM and the heat sink. (vi)

Eighty percent of the enormous amounts of heat and energy that will be produced in the fusion process will escape in the form of fast neutrons (14.1 MeV). Since these particles have no charge, they cannot be redirected by means of a magnetic field to a specific location. This has been one of the greatest engineering challenges from the outset, as the entire FW will be exposed to an intense bombardment of highly energetic neutrons; therefore, the components that will face the plasma must meet several indispensable design criteria:

- Be strong enough to withstand such high radiation and temperature. The material chosen should have good thermal conductivity to easily evacuate heat, but at the same time cannot be readily activated, as the components are expected to last at least 20 years before being replaced.
- Be capable of effectively dissipating such heat, which, recovered through a cold water circuit, will be the heat that will generate electrical power in a realistic NPP. For a material to be considered as a potential PFM component, good compatibility with the hot fusion plasma, i.e., a low atomic number, Z , is a must, as well as an excellent *sputter* (a physical process in which atoms in a solid-state (target) are released and pass into the gas phase by bombardment with energetic ions) resistance.
- Alternatively, tokamaks with high- Z materials such as tungsten (W) must be operated in such a way as to guarantee that the net impurity influx into the plasma should be so low that the critical impurity concentration is not exceeded. This is due to the fact that since this material has a high Z , it cannot be completely ionized, causing some of its electrons to remain free and radiate energy, thus cooling the plasma

A brief analysis of the loads that the PFCs will undergo in the upcoming fusion experimental projects is presented in **Table 1**. It can be seen that the step between ITER and DEMO is much larger than between DEMO and *PROTO* (DEMO's successor, expected to become the first

commercial nuclear fusion reactor after 2050), hence the need for an intermediate materials testing facility between ITER and DEMO.

Table 1. Loads suffered by the PFCs in the FW. Adapted from Ref. [16].

	ITER	DEMO	PROTO	Units
Heat flux	0.3	0.5	0.5	MW/m ²
Fusion power	0.5	2.5	5	GW
Neutron damage	<3	80	150	dpa
Neutron load	0.78	<2	2	MW/m ²
Neutron load in life	0.07	8	15	MW-years/m ²

The neutron load is the energy of the 14-MeV neutrons from the D–T reaction which pass through the FW. Although they are not deposited in the FW, they can damage it. The neutron load accumulated over the lifetime of each project is the parameter that really matters. This is substantially larger for a reactor than it is for ITER because a reactor should last for roughly 15 years before it needs to be upgraded. ITER is only an experiment. The longer the material is exposed to a neutron flux, the more frequently one of its atoms will be knocked out of place by a neutron. After many dpa events, the material will swell or shrink and become so brittle as to be useless.

By 2050, DEMO is estimated to have the capacity to supply 100 MW of net power to the grid and operate on a closed fuel cycle. However, for this to happen, the materials need to overcome much tougher conditions than those they will face in ITER. The need to include sufficient flexibility in the design of DEMO to accommodate improvements in plasma performance and design of core components is indispensable.

The main aims of DEMO are to:

- Achieve T self-sufficiency.
- Solve all physical and technical issues related to the plant and demonstrate reactor-related technology.
- Achieve adequate availability/reliability operation over a *reasonable time span* (while ITER is expected to work with 400 s pulses and a long dwell time, DEMO will work with long pulses (>2 h) or even at a steady state)

Materials for the DEMO reactor must be chosen considering the high doses of irradiation produced by neutrons with a thermonuclear reaction energy spectrum and the very high heat load

on the inner wall of the chamber. This can lead to significant in-vessel material damage. It will be necessary to develop and test new materials for constructing the DEMO thermonuclear reactor and solve issues related to their commercial-scale manufacture.

The blanket supposed to be used in ITER is in fact unsuitable for the future DEMO thermonuclear reactor. The envisaged materials can only withstand a small neutron flux and the exit coolant temperature is too low to ensure efficient power generation. The next step after ITER is to elaborate the design of DEMO and a thermonuclear power plant. Their linear dimensions will be about 50% larger than those of ITER, and their fusion power will be 5 and 7 times higher, respectively.

It appears that pilot plants and reactors may experience rates of net erosion and deposition of PFC material in the range of 10^3 – 10^4 kg/year, values well above those expected in ITER. The deposition of such massive quantities of material has the potential to interfere with pilot plant and reactor operation and to seriously compromise the safety of the DT cycle. For example, elevated dust levels due to exfoliated and detached deposits can lead to a high risk of dust explosion. Other adverse effects due to the accumulation of unwanted eroded material at critical locations could result in the appearance of cracks in the cooling channels due to thermal stress.

The DEMO design and R&D activities will benefit largely from the strongest experimental supporting evidence that will be gained from the design, construction and operation of ITER. Due to the *differences* (in terms of size and, especially, in terms of ITER's wider mission) between the two devices, not all ITER solutions are directly applicable to DEMO.

4.1. Tungsten

Nowadays, tungsten is considered the most efficient material for components facing high heat flux, mainly due to its high melting point ($T=3422^\circ=3422^\circ\text{C}$), good thermal conductivity (160 W/m·K), excellent high temperature stability and low T retention.

However, major concerns regarding the use of W in fusion reactor applications include its inherent brittleness at low temperature and the embrittlement due to recrystallization and neutron irradiation. To overcome these drawbacks, several efforts have been made to modify W through grain refining, alloying, dispersion of secondary phases, and formation of composites.

Although W and CFCs were initially considered as the most promising PFMs, the fact is that at the end of 2013, the decision was made to discard CFCs due to their tendency to retain T and to opt for a fully tungsten-armoured divertor.

A *single null divertor* (characterised by toroidal symmetry and one X-point or “null”) is to be installed in the bottom area of the VV of the ITER tokamak. It will extract the heat and ash produced in the fusion reaction, minimize plasma contamination and protect the surrounding walls from thermal and neutron fluxes.

Specifically, the divertor will consist of 54 divertor cassette assemblies (CAs) operated by remote handling (**Figure 3**). Each of these CAs includes a cassette body (CB) and three PFCs, namely the internal and external vertical targets (IVT and OVT) and the dome. In addition, each of these modules will house diagnostic components for plasma control, evaluation and optimization.

Figure 3. Parts of one of the 54 divertor modules. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [11]. Credit © ITER Organization, 2019.

The IVTs and OVTs are placed at the intersection of the magnetic field lines where the particle bombardment will be particularly intense in ITER. The heat flux to which these components are subjected is estimated to be between 10 and 20 MW/m². Materials and cooling methods that

cannot be used in the FW may be used in the divertor, mainly due to the presence of coils located at the bottom of the chamber that bend the outermost field lines to enter the divertor.

4.1.1. ITER Design

During the last decades, several PFC designs have been developed with W. The most efficient are the monoblock and flat-tile types.

These models (**Figure 4**) consist of modules that have been machined from a PFM and attached to a water-cooled heat sink made of a metallic alloy. The joints between the PFM and the heat sink must acquire very high mechanical strength to tolerate the high temperatures and keep the modules uniformly in position. Each of these is equipped with a cylindrical hole necessary for the junction between the PFM and the heat sink usually made of CuCrZr.

Figure 4. Main PFC designs for ITER. The charged particles depositing their energy are guided by the magnetic field lines. (a) Monoblock design. (b) Flat tile design. Reprinted from Ref

Despite its good performance, the flat tile design (**Figure 4b**) presents the possibility of local overheating of the shielding plate due to the incidence of plasma particles. The loss of even a single tile is considered a rather serious event, as it would lead to the degradation of joints in the adjacent tiles (so-called cascade failure).

Therefore, it has been decided that the ITER divertor will be completely made of monoblock W due to its greater robustness versus possible accident conditions. Thus, both IVTs and OVTs will be completely covered with this water-cooled material

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4.1.2. Smart Alloys

Due to its excellent properties, W has also been chosen as a prime PFM candidate for DEMO. However, certain accidental models have revealed several drawbacks related to the use of pure W. Those are its intrinsic low temperature brittleness, neutron-induced embrittlement and recrystallization resistance. To prevent this, new modalities have been developed and tested under fusion-relevant conditions. These include the modification of its granular structure and the combination with several alloying elements and compounds (Mo, Ti, Y_2O_3 , ...) to increase strength and recrystallization resistance. The latter are the so-called *smart alloys* (which automatically adapt their properties to the environment (SA))

One of the major concerns of using pure W in DEMO is related to its behavior under a LOCA with air ingress in the VV. Under those circumstances, the temperature of the tungsten cladding could reach 1000 °C and remain at such a high level for several weeks. Tungsten oxidizes and radioactive, neutron-activated tungsten oxide sublimates into the environment at such a high temperature.

During an accident, the remaining alloying elements in the bulk will diffuse to the surface and form their own oxides, protecting tungsten from oxidation and subsequent sublimation into the atmosphere. Recent studies have demonstrated the benefits of systems based on W-Cr-Y, which are produced by *mechanical alloying* (a ball milling process where a powder mixture placed in the ball mill is subjected to a high-energy collision from the balls. The process is usually carried out in an inert atmosphere) (MA) and compacted by FAST. These SA have demonstrated very high oxidation resistance and contain Cr as an oxidizing alloying element and Y as an active element stabilizing and regulating the chromium transport in the alloy system.

Despite all their development, there are still open questions in both the understanding of the physics and the technological development of SA systems. The role of Y in the stabilization of a W-Cr solid solution still needs to be further understood as well as the technology of joining SAs with the corresponding structural materials. At the same time, the scale of fabrication at the

industrial level needs to be improved. Finally, it is of vital importance to carry out a thorough evaluation of the effect of neutrons and impurities as well as transmutation on alloy performance.

5. Structural Materials

It is clear that in order to achieve projects of the nature of ITER or DEMO it is necessary to develop materials to their maximum potential, with the clear objective of withstanding the extreme conditions of temperature, irradiation damage and production of transmutation elements.

According to L. Malerba et al. [54], a structural material is one that is manufactured for the purpose of withstanding large amounts of stress, whether its origin is mechanical, thermal, vibrational, etc. These materials can be divided into two types:

- *Replaceable*: Designed to be relatively easy to remove from the reactor. An example would be the fuel assemblies in a nuclear power plant.
- *Non-replaceable*: They constitute the main structure of the reactor, so they are designed to mitigate the greatest possible degradation caused by external agents. An example would be the FW components.

It is evident that there is a strong overlap with nuclear fission materials research. However, fusion materials present a few additional challenges. The first of these is the large amount of He that is produced, both in the D-T fusion reaction and by transmutation reactions in the structure. These He bubbles that form at vacancies and GB cause swelling and embrittlement, which extensively degrades the materials. The second effect that is unique to fusion reactors is associated with the 14 MeV fast neutron. This high-energy particle penetrates deep into the structure and collides with the lattice atoms, creating numerous defects in the material. The accumulation of this damage in the structural and diagnostic materials is one of the main headaches in the design of this type of reactors.

Structural materials consist of crystals that adopt certain arrangements in some atoms of their lattice. Metals and alloys usually consist of regions with many crystals called grains, whose boundaries are the aforementioned GB. Ionizing radiation gives off more or less energy to the material depending on the type and energy of the particle and the medium in which it is found. This radiation-material interaction is what generates the defects, which depend directly on the initial defects of the unirradiated sample. The origin of the atomistic defects is given by:

- Transmutation reactions. (i)
- Atomic displacements due to nuclear stopping power. (ii)

Ionization and excitation due to electronic stopping power. (iii)

The structural materials that make up the cooling pipes of the BB of the reactor, responsible for T production, electrical generation and radiation protection, will be subject to a severe operating environment, with damage from fast neutron irradiation, high temperature and high stress. Requirements for these structural materials include low activation, good compatibility with different coolants, resistance to irradiation and high temperatures, among others.

Thus far, three main candidates for low activation structural materials have been proposed for the FW. These are in order of relevance RAFM steels, SiC/SiC ceramic composites and vanadium alloys.

5.2.1. Plasma Facing Components

Numerous PFC concept studies are currently underway due to the good compatibility between W-SiC (in terms of thermal expansion, bonding technology and operating temperature window) [86,87]. The development of technology to join SiC/SiC with itself or with other materials is essential for their integration into various nuclear applications. These bonds are intended to provide mechanical robustness, tolerance to neutron irradiation and a certain chemical stability in the operating environment [80]. When W is reinforced with a ceramic material such as silicon carbide, a so-called metal matrix composite is produced. SiC-reinforced W metal matrix composites have been fabricated and shown to present favorable properties, such as increased resistance to corrosion and abrasion.

Following the Fukushima disaster, SiC-based cladding was proposed to replace the current zircaloy and is also one of the leading candidates for use as a structural protective layer for fuel particles in Gen IV reactors. This research has significantly advanced fabrication technology as well as the understanding of material properties. Due to common technological hurdles, these technologies and insights can be applied to the development of fusion materials.

5.3.2. Near Future

As an advanced choice of structural materials for fusion applications, the manufacturing technology of V alloys has made great advances in recent years. Research on coating and corrosion, irradiation damage or H isotope retention has also progressed considerably. However, critical problems related to high temperature operation and low temperature embrittlement of the material remain to be solved.

Because efforts in recent years have focused more on a mature candidate such as RAFM, progress in the development of V-alloys slowed down as compared to a decade ago. Despite this and because advanced options need to be explored in order to mitigate risk and provide a higher long-term performance option, research into these materials is crucial and can be achieved through efficient use of the available infrastructure.

From this point of view, exploring new advanced materials to improve their performance becomes more meaningful. One example may be the coating of V alloys in the FW with shielding materials, such as W layers, by a vacuum plasma spraying method (VPS).

Finally, for a near future development it is worth mentioning the effort being made in assessing high-entropy alloys (HEAs). By creating HEAs from elements with favourable properties in terms of nuclear activation, materials that can withstand the nuclear fusion environment can be manufactured while minimising the radioactive waste produced. Such a material could be used in the extreme thermal and irradiation conditions of a fusion blanket as they demonstrate impressive combinations of attractive properties such as high strength and high fracture toughness. In addition, these alloys may demonstrate superior irradiation damage tolerance due to high lattice distortion and sluggish diffusion from multiple principal elements in HEAs.

These alloys, which are multi-element, equiatomic metallic systems, can crystallize in a single phase despite having high concentrations (20–25 atomic percent) of various elements with different crystal structures [99]. Fascinating new materials may emerge as this subject develops. Nevertheless, there have been no studies done on FCC alloys containing V, and theoretical conclusions to date have only been drawn on a small range of alloys.

Conclusions

The problems of developing, testing, verifying and ultimately qualifying materials for the fusion reactor vessel environment are one of the great materials research challenges of recent times. The situation is very complex due in large part to the urgency of developing fusion reactors to meet the planet's energy and environmental needs.

The development of ITER has been a giant step forward. Important measures that have been done to address important issues include the initiation of multiple irradiation campaigns, advanced high heat flux simulations, as well as the continued development of multi-scale models

of materials. The lack of technologically ready materials is clearly a concern for DEMO, aiming to facilitate more effective planning and targeted materials development in line with EURO fusion's strategic plans.

For the range of operating conditions expected in ITER and with even greater relevance for DEMO, a qualified database must be generated to demonstrate that candidate materials meet a series of indispensable design requirements. Throughout this paper, several materials have been analyzed, from the most studied and used today such as W, RAFM steels and Be, to the most promising ones for future projects such as SiC composites, V-alloys or ODS steels among others.

Although the materials for ITER are already defined, long-term development does not stop and hundreds of studies are being carried out to find new materials or manufacturing techniques that can be used in ITER to overcome the even more difficult and demanding conditions of DEMO. Numerous promising designs have been discarded, which shows the commitment of the nuclear industry to constantly strive for the highest possible degree of perfection and safety.

Technologies such as tritium generation have received special emphasis within the ITER R&D program, as it is expected to have a major impact in the future. For this reason, a review has been made of the different blanket designs that are being considered, as well as the materials that can contribute to a greater extent to a better efficiency.

Clearly, there is a strong overlap with nuclear fission materials research; however, fusion materials present a few additional challenges. Structural materials will suffer a severe operating environment, with damage from fast neutron irradiation, high temperature, and high stress. Requirements for these structural materials include low activation, good compatibility with various coolants, and irradiation resistance, among others. Thus far, three main candidates for low-activation structural materials have been proposed for the FW. These are—in order of relevance— RAFM steels, SiC/SiC ceramic composites and V-alloys.

For their part, diagnostic systems will play a key role in the control of the fusion process and will allow us to achieve a better understanding of plasma physics. To achieve this, the tokamak must be equipped with sensors and instrumentation to fully explore the operating environment. Finally, one of the major limitations is related to the difficulty of reproducing a realistic fusion neutron spectrum to test candidate materials for DEMO. Fortunately, the development of IFMIF-DONES seems to solve this problem. In fact, some of the most advanced materials, such as Cu alloys, W or RAFM steels, will be studied in this facility.

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